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Report of the First International Workshop on Horizon Scanning for Plant Health

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), French
Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational
Health & Safety (ANSES) and European Commission
– Joint Research Centre (JRC)

Abstract

This report summarizes the First International Workshop on Horizon Scanning for Plant Health, held on April 9-10, 2024, at the ANSES headquarters in Maisons-Alfort, France. The main goal of this first workshop was to facilitate discussions and exchanges among risk assessors and scientists involved in Horizon Scanning (HS from now on) in the field of biological invasions. Participants shared experiences, knowledge, and explored innovative approaches. Additionally, the workshop aimed to explore the possibilities and interest on the creation of a HS community in the field of plant health and more in general of biological invasions.

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Keywords: artificial intelligence, biological invasion, collaboration, One Health, preparedness, text mining, web scraping

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Summary

Since 2017, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) is mandated by the European Commission (EC) to conduct horizon scanning activity in the field of plant health. This activity is performed in collaboration with the EC Joint Research Centre (JRC) and the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES). The aim of this activity is to capture signals from the web about potential threats caused by plant pests from all around the world and to convey them to EU risk managers in order to support their preparedness and timely reactions. This activity has produced more than 120 newsletters and three technical reports. ANSES has been awarded with a grant to support EFSA with scientific and technical assistance on horizon scanning from 2022 to 2026 in the context of crisis preparedness on plant health of the EU territory (GP/EFSA/PLANTS/2022/07)", that includes a series of workshops and webinars in the aim to support communication and dissemination of the horizon scanning approach and to build a community of risk assessors and risk managers involved in such activities.

For these reasons, on the 9th and 10th of April 2024, the First International Workshop on Horizon Scanning for Plant Health was held in the headquarters of ANSES (Maisons-Alfort, France).

This first workshop aimed to provide a platform for risk assessors, scientists, researchers, academics, to share experiences, knowledge, and explore innovative approaches related to horizon scanning, applicable and/or applied in the context of plant health and more broadly, biological invasions.

A second workshop will focus on the risk managers and their perspective and needs as end-users of the project's outputs. While, bringing together the outcomes from both events, a third workshop will be organised to analyse risk drivers: exploring how factors influencing future pest invasion events should be considered. Finally, a fourth and last workshop will be held by the end of 2026 where, collaboratively, the most effective practices and priorities for horizon scanning will be defined.

This report describes main content and outcomes of the First International Workshop on Horizon Scanning for Plant Health. It includes the list of participants, the agenda, brief summaries of the contributions by keynote speakers and other participants, content of the groups discussions and results of survey, and conclusions with future perspectives. A self-evaluation of horizon scanning was followed through the event but also after through the feedback received by the participants.

Trying to bring together all the different tools, methodologies and perspectives had the scope to map the current horizon scanning activities worldwide, and should act as a basis for the creation of a community of professionals involved in projects of horizon scanning in the field of plant health.

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Introduction

Since 2017, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), at the request of the European Commission (EC), has been conducting horizon scanning (HS from now on) in the field of plant health. This initiative is carried out in collaboration with the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC-ISPRA) and the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES). The primary aim is to capture web signals from media and scientific literature about potential threats caused worldwide by plant pests. These signals are summarized in a monthly newsletter, highlighting the most relevant ones to EU risk manager, in support to their preparedness and timely reactions.

In the context of the partnership renewed between EFSA and ANSES from 2022 to 2026 (EFSA Art 36 grant GP/EFSA/PLANTS/2022/07), a series of workshops and webinars have been planned. Their objectives are to: (i) support the dissemination of the EFSA HS approach; (ii) ensure the timely communication of HS results; and (iii) strengthen global HS in Plant Health by initiating a worldwide community.

This workshop is the first of a series of four that are planned to be held between 2024 and 2026 and is meant to bring together researchers from academia and risk assessment across the EU and also from overseas, to understand the diversity of activities and methods that can be identified as HS and to start discussions on the necessity of a HS community, enriched by the different approaches and experiences.

The second workshop will focus on how HS supports the risk managers. More specifically, the risk managers priorities and needs will be identified with the aim to ensure effective and fit for the purpose technical support.

Following, bringing together the outcomes from both events, a third workshop will be organised to discuss the drivers of the threatening biological invasions, exploring how factors influencing future events should be considered.

A final workshop will be held where, collaboratively within the established community at that time, the most effective practices and priorities for HS will be further defined and fine-tuned.

The report includes the list of participants, the agenda, presentations from keynote speakers and other contributors, the main topics discussed, results from survey, and conclusions with future perspectives. An auto-evaluation of the involvement of the participants in the HS was conducted during the event. Bringing together various tools, methodologies, and perspectives will help map current HS activities and serve as a basis for creating a cohesive community.

Objective of the workshop

The First International Workshop on HS for Plant Health aimed to provide an opportunity for risk assessors, scientists, researchers, and academics to share experiences, knowledge, and explore innovative approaches related to HS in the context of plant health and biological invasions.

The whole event has been conceived as an informal meeting where each participant was engaged and stimulated to actively participate and bring added value within the context. The initial goal was therefore to create the right conditions to allow participants feeling part of a group, identifying commonalities and differences in goals, ways of working and results.

The final objective of the event is to initiate the building of a community dedicated to HS in Plant Health with the intent to facilitate the sharing of knowledge, research findings, and best practices resulting from the HS activities. On the long term, the relevance of a community is ensured by

the regular discussion among members, provision of webinars, guest talks by experts, collaborations on projects or research that address common challenges or areas of interest.

The engagement of the community members in the activities is therefore an essential key to the success of the whole process.

Participants

The event was initially conceived as a targeted workshop in person, with a limited number of participants: the physical attendance was encouraged to enhance interpersonal relations and exchanges between participants. However, due to geographical and business boundaries, not all selected invitees could make it and in order not to miss their participation, as a secondary choice also remote participation was allowed.

The composition of the participants list was crucial to the achievement of the preliminary objective of the event, such as the stimulation to look for creative solutions and alternative options, including the challenging of the individual ways of working.

For these reasons, participants were primarily from academia and public institutions selected and invited for their particular involvement in research using or developing HS approaches or closely related topics. In addition to experts on plant health, on data mining and early detection, also experts on invasion ecology and animal health were invited. A particular role was played by JRC and WHO representatives who are today ensuring the existence of the EIOS platform, that has the potential to host the first worldwide plant health community in line with the One Health approach.

In Appendix A, the table with the list of the participants, their affiliation and their role during the event is provided.

Presentations and summary of the discussions

Philippe Reignault Head of ANSES Plant Health Laboratory & Scientific Director for Plant Health opened the event welcoming the participants to the first international workshop on horizon scanning in plant health. The ANSES mission, activities and structure were presented. The role of the multiannual partnership between ANSES, EFSA and EC-JRC for preparing the EU to new biological invasions was highlighted. He also reminded the importance of developing this activity in line with the One Health approach, a goal shared by the three above mentioned institutions.

The following brainstorming session was introduced by the anonymous survey to all participants (19 in person, excluding the 7 organizers, and 20 online, from 18 countries distributed among all continents). The reactions and answers were shared in real time in order to stimulate discussion and to highlight the variety of the group, with specific needs and expertise and how to make this richness of use to the effective running of the workshop. The survey was conducted in two steps: one at the beginning of day 1 and the second at the end of day 2 and the summary of main results is provided in section 6 of this report.

Keynote speakers:

Philip Hulme - Distinguished Professor of Plant Biosecurity, Centre for One Biosecurity Research, Analysis and Synthesis, Lincoln University, New Zealand - Horizon Scanning for biosecurity: a false dawn?

Topic: challenges for future thinking

Summary: assessment and management of biosecurity are mainly limited by data availability about both likelihood and consequences of invasions. Horizon scanning (HS) in particular is a foresight approach applicable in those conditions of very limited knowledge about both likelihood and consequences (limits of biosafety and biosecurity knowledge). Moving from insights to farsight (therefore from limited uncertainty and time horizon to broader ones), the approaches go through different stages from insight (environmental scanning), trend analysis (risk) to foresight (horizon scanning and then scenario modelling). Environmental scanning and HS are frequently confused. The DPSIR (Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response) framework provides a holistic approach aiming at identifying the different types and levels of possible responses available to risk managers. It delivers indicators needed to enable feedback to policy makers on plant health and protection, and the resulting impact of the political choices made or to be made in the future. A number of studies are brought as example, highlighting strengths and shortcomings, among which stand out the importance of common frameworks and holistic approaches, the interdisciplinarity and gender balance of expert groups, the definition of clear roadmaps.

Keywords: biosecurity, environmental scanning, driver mapping, timeline, audience, policies, roadmap, clear goal, interdisciplinary, balance, DPSIR components, PESTLE drivers

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Topics of questions:

- Involvement of indigenous scientists and stakeholders should also be taken into account in defining the appropriate composition of an expert group and/or structures to be consulted.
- The timeline role in distinguishing environmental scanning and true HS¹: the first is reactive to a contingent problem, while the second is meant to test the system and identify the most appropriate model to target a specific issue.
- The possibility to have IPPC driving a thematic assessment of plant health globally could be considered.
- Measuring the effectiveness of the HS process would require a periodical (e.g. after 10 years) review of the consequent actions undertaken by the targeted audiences, from farmers to risk managers, in response to the generated alert.
- Resource allocation to differentiate between signals and artefactual noise and to avoid a long list of pests.

Cindy E. Morris – Research director – Plant pathology research unit, INRAE Avignon, France – Sustainable plant production based on insight from One Health: what will be the scope and targets for horizon scanning?

Topic: connecting One Health and Horizon Scanning

Summary: the concept of One Health is based on the interdependence of the health of all the organisms through natural and human driven processes. The case presented is the application of One Health perspective to surveillance of plant diseases. This requires extending the analysis to other fields and disciplines, overlooked epidemiological processes and applying new tools and methodologies at more diverse scales. The examples provided here refer to i) reservoirs outside agriculture, and on substrates other than plants (ex: new habitats and soil), ii) virulence factors that can also be adaptations for survival in the environment, iii) framework for assessing potential risk of microbial lines before they emerge as pathogens, iv) spill-over via natural processes that disseminate constantly and at long distance pathogens (sporadically-occurring and ubiquitous ones). With this modern approach, preparedness towards new epidemiological events and also surveillance activity can be improved and cope with limited traditional data availability: long-term perspective, opportunistic data, space-distant phenomena and indirect pest observations provide further insights in support to risk preparedness. Furthermore, One Health contributes to enhance sustainability of agriculture by integrating indicators of ecosystem services that foster plant, animal, soil, and human health.

¹ Hulme PE, 2024. Trouble on the horizon: anticipating biological invasions through futures thinking. *Biological Reviews* <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/brv.13149> [Published after the workshop]

Keywords: drivers, soil, sustainable agriculture, spillover, pathogenicity, host range, genetics, ecosystem, prevention, reservoirs

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Topics of questions:

- Predicting models for host range, which determine the pathogenicity, could help in prevention.
- Soil as a new ecosystem from where global health starts and co-infections as part of the pathogen ecosystem.
- Studying pathogens from One Health perspective could help to define movement patterns.

Susan Canavan – Botanist, Horizon Scanning Consultant - On the Horizon: Identifying invasive species threats in the United States

Topic: horizon scanning for invasive species

Summary: Identification of US invasive species in Florida by HS, focusing on identifying high-risk species and pathways. Utilizing tools like the CABI HS tool, thousands of species were filtered using different criteria such as synonym correction, climate matching, regulatory and non-regulatory databases, GloNAF database for naturalized plants, weedy history, expert knowledge and GBIF. After the data-based list processing and a rapid risk assessment, the conclusion for each species was obtained by consensus. The result was a ranked list of species from which a shortlist for a national early detection rapid response framework was obtained. Capturing trends could help moving from environmental scanning to HS. Examples in the application of new technologies and tools such as culturomics and iEcology are given. The importance of incorporating more data on human driven trends (e.g. trade) and automatize analysis in order to process big amount of data are highlighted (e.g. statistical analysis, temporal and trend analysis, sentiment analysis, content analysis of digital data collected from social networks).

Keywords: taxonomy, databases, weedy, early detection, shortlist, risk assessment, culture, automatic process, sentiment analysis, ecology

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Topics of questions:

- The sources used for this study may lead to a loss of information for the unknown. By using social media, the interpretation of trends have to be carefully conducted e.g.: more followers of certain topics can be driven by a general increase in the number of accounts, or number of mentions of certain invasive species could be driven by the higher attractiveness of the species.

Tools and technologies

Johannes Schnitzler – EIOS: Epidemic Intelligence from Open Sources. A global initiative led by the World Health Organization

Topic: EIOS (<https://www.who.int/initiatives/eios>)

Summary: the WHO Hub for Pandemic and Epidemic Intelligence (<https://pandemichub.who.int/>) is working towards a world where collaborative surveillance empowers countries and communities to minimise the impact of pandemic and epidemic threats. The Epidemic Intelligence from Open Sources (EIOS) Initiative is led by WHO is part of the Hub. The EIOS initiative is built on three pillars: a growing global community of practice, a range of multi-disciplinary collaborators and an evolving fit-for-purpose EIOS system. EIOS is a web-based system supporting global public health intelligence activities, providing relevant publicly available information from a broad range of sources. EIOS follows an all-hazard/one-health approach and provides a collaborative working spaces, where partners can easily connect and join surveillance efforts. EIOS has been adopted by over 85 member states and over 20 organizations and networks. Current and future functionalities, features and structure of the platform are described. Having also plant health as part of EIOS community is in line with One Health approach.

Keywords: public health intelligence, artificial intelligence, collaboration, community, public health, sources

Topics of questions:

- Allergies is a topic currently not covered, and is a good example of connection of categories between communities (i.e. plant health and medicine) that the system can support.
- EIOS communities can define the level of collaboration and sharing of information with others, although the direction of the project is toward fostering cross collaborations and sharing workloads.
- Not always high-volume events correspond to high risks: the role of experts using EIOS is in fact that of interpreting the relevance of such events.
- Open sources and copyright conflicts were mentioned, as well as the definition of events and signals.

Kristina Kovacicova – Machine learning specialist – DISINFO unit, European Commission Joint Research Centre - Analysis of disinformation narrative: climate change

Topic: combating disinformation through artificial intelligence and other tools

Summary: Since 2019, the team mission is to support EU commission services by processing news, detecting disinformation, and providing analysis and reports. Initially focused on COVID-19 (e.g.: anti-vaccination narratives), the current priorities include climate change, migration, and conflicts (Russia-Ukraine and Israel-Gaza). This is done by using text classification and clustering models to analyse narratives and Large Language Models (LLMs) to understand the context within clusters and generate summaries (e.g., key arguments in articles). Key findings include shifts in disinformation topics, and persuasion techniques. The final outcome is the analysis of long-term trends, new narratives and domains to identify and understand disinformation campaigns.

Keywords: classification of text, large-language models, keywords, trends, context

References:

Piskorski J, Stefanovitch N, Nikolaidis N, Da San Martino G and Preslav Nakov, 2023. Multilingual Multifaceted Understanding of Online News in Terms of Genre, Framing, and Persuasion Techniques. In Proceedings of the 61st Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers), pages 3001–3022, Toronto, Canada. Association for Computational Linguistics.

Topics of questions:

- Sources identified as responsible for disinformation can still represent relevant sources of information. Persuasion techniques themselves are not disinformation.
- LLMs have the potential to generate new categories once they are trained through clustering. Data augmentation has also the potential to improve the results quality.
- The type of persuasion techniques applied is influenced by the type of source where they are applied, culture, country, etc. It could be interesting to track the preferred persuasion techniques in scientific publications and if any trend in their use exists.
- The representativeness of the team performing annotation campaigns is pointed out as a sensitive aspect in ensuring unbiased outcomes.

Mathieu Roche – Text mining

Topic: Plant Health - PADI-web (<https://plant.padi-web.cirad.fr/en/>)

Summary:

The Platform for Automated extraction of Disease Information from the web (PADI-web) has been developed initially for animal health surveillance, and recently for plant disease surveillance. In order to identify relevant news and information with this new PADI-web instance dedicated to plant health, machine learning approaches and language models have been integrated for monitoring plant diseases. PADI-web algorithms for specific case studies (i.e. *Xylella fastidiosa*, *Fusarium oxysporum* Tropical, Huanglongbing) uses text mining approaches fine-tuned on the plant disease domain. The system proposes automatic classification of texts, notifications of events to end-users and maps for plant health monitoring in different countries. In future work, the plan is to evaluate how these visualisations and language model methods can improve the identification of (i) weak signals and (ii) duplication of events. Moreover, syndromic surveillance tasks implemented for animal health monitoring could be adapted for plant health surveillance.

Keywords: data collection, text mining, classification

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Roche M, Rabatel J, Trevennec C and Pieretti I, 2024. PADI-web for Plant Health Surveillance. In: Intelligent information systems: CAiSE Forum 2024, Limassol, Cyprus, June 3–7, 2024, Proceedings. Islam Shareeful (ed.), Sturn Arnon (ed.). Cham: Springer, 148-156. (Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing, 520) ISBN 978-3-031-60999-2

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James Cullum – Artificial Intelligence tool for reducing noise

Topic: PlantWisePlus (<https://www.cabi.org/plantwiseplus/>)

Summary: CABI's PlantwisePlus program helps low-income countries fight crop loss from new plant threats. The aim is to generate a newsletter system to alert NPPOs to changing pest risks, based on monitoring of a list of pests that each country considers as potential risks. The newsletters have been named Pest Risk Monitoring Reports or 'PRiM' Reports. This HS activity uses web monitoring via EIOS and machine learning. The machine learning model is under continuous improvement by feeding it with positive (by promoting) and negative (by demoting) inputs, with the scope of reducing the noise elements and the amount of manual activity in preparing reports to NPPOs. CABI is also building capacity with NPPOs to maintain Pest Risk Registers; databases listing potential plant threats ranked by overall risk of entry and establishment in the country, and magnitude of socio-economic and environmental impacts. Used in conjunction with information provided in regular PRiM reports, NPPOs can make informed decisions about appropriate follow-on actions and how to allocate resources to prevent the arrival of new pests. This HS activity uses web monitoring via EIOS and machine learning.

Keywords: machine learning model, text scraping, accuracy, NPPO, newsletter, list of pests

Challenge of the workshop

The main goal of this workshop was to identify and find solutions to common challenges in HS, such as data sharing, copyright issues, and managing large volumes of data.

This can only be achieved by enhancing collaboration between institutions, by promoting international cooperation and building a community of practice to improve HS activities.

Ideally this would result in better supporting preparedness of the decision makers to better protect our agriculture and environment, thus providing insights and recommendations to help risk managers to anticipate and to respond to emerging plant health threats.

The workshop brought together experts from several continents, institutions and backgrounds to discuss innovative approaches and share knowledge on plant health and biological invasions. The focus was on HS as a tool for early detection and management of plant health threats.

Given the wide range of topics covered by HS, sharing knowledge and best practices among participants is crucial. This exchange helps to understand the needs of users and developers, ensuring that the goals set for building a community to identify plant health threats are realistic and effective.

To ensure effective and up-to-date HS activities, it is essential to explore innovative approaches and discuss new methodologies and tools. This is particularly important given the major technological breakthroughs, including the integration of AI in work processes and in tools for pest detection and diagnosis.

Survey results

At the beginning of the first day of the workshop, a survey was conducted to analyse the expectations and prior knowledge of the participants. At the end of the event, a second round of survey was conducted in order to assess the workshop outcome in terms of trend of engagement and awareness of participants.

As a starting point, the expectations of participants were strongly focused on networking and knowledge exchange, which fits with the workshop objectives: the agenda (available in Appendix B) included the opportunity for each participant to share information on their projects and identified best practices. Participants were interested in learning how the others work to identify emerging plant health risks and invasive species. There was an intention to address issues like risk analysis, decision support systems, and early warning systems. This included understanding the current state of HS, new approaches and methodologies, and potential areas of collaboration. Building a community was another key theme. Participants aimed to connect in a structured manner with others working in the field and to have facilitated conditions for knowledge sharing. Beyond networking and threat detection, participants expressed a desire to learn new methods and explore broader perspectives. This included understanding the role of One Health, expertise in areas like ecological modelling, data analysis, artificial intelligence (AI) and Natural Language Processing (NLP) applied to HS.

The participants were broadly categorized into three main areas: i) invasive species and plant health, ii) early warning and detection (Early warning systems, citizen science, emerging threats), iii) reporting (HS and information databases and risk communication). Given the different backgrounds of participants they were asked to provide their definition for HS; here are listed some of the received answers:

- proactive threat identification,
- early detection of emerging risks,
- analysing vast information for potential issues,
- prioritizing risk assessment based on scan results,
- resource allocation in management of information overload.

The type of activities involved in the HS process can be clustered among three main categories of actions:

- Monitoring: data is gathered from various sources and is utilized to monitor and find out the trends and patterns in the environment.
- Analysing/Synthesizing: retrospective and forward-looking analysis in order to identify emerging trends and estimate future events.
- Communicating: delivery of results to risk managers and/or other final users

After having provided these definitions to the participants, they were asked to select in which part of the process they were mainly involved. The distribution of dots in the Figure 2 indicates that most of users participate throughout the entire process, with only few of them being specialised on certain aspects.

Figure 2. Involvement of users in the different activities composing the horizon scanning process (Monitoring, Analysis/Synthesizing, Communicating). Each dot indicates where the user considers contributing the most during her/his horizon scanning activity the overlapping dots are represented with numbers.

In further elaboration of these categories, we name four factors that are drivers in designing and performing HS activity: i) data availability, ii) selection of the tool use to collect the information, iii) method applied to assess and forecast risks, and iv) the final audience to which the HS activity is targeted. Participants positioned their score for each driver within a Cartesian plane considering both the impact on the tasks and resources involved in the HS (process) and the impact on the final outcomes of the activity (results). This same question was asked before and after the workshop (Figure 3, a and b).

Figure 3. Distribution of drivers influencing process and results in the horizon scanning activity: during the monitoring phase (Data availability, Tool used to collect information), during the analysis and synthesis (Assessing and forecasting method) and during the communication (Final audience). X axis to impact on the process and Y axis corresponds to impact on the result. Each dot averages the score given by all users (1st answer n = 30; 2nd answer n=18).

Data availability emerged in a constant manner as the most impacting driver, with an average score of 7/10 for its impact on the process itself, and 8.4/10 on the outcomes. These scores increased further by the second day, reaching 8/10 and 9/10, respectively.

The tool applied in the HS activity remained also consistent with a 6.8/10 for the process and 5.8/10 for the result.

The other two factors fluctuated more significantly between the two rounds, both increasing their weight from the first to the second survey: i) the method, initially rated for process at 5.7/10 moved to 6.9/10, and for results from 6.6/10 to 7/10; ii) the audience moved from 4.5/10 to 6/10 for the process and from 5.6/10 to 6.9/10 for the results.

Concerning the tools applied by users for HS activity, the average percentages assigned were: Web Scraping and Monitoring Tools 20%, Data Visualization Tools 10%; Early Warning Systems 10%; Trend and Network Analysis 9,7 and 9,5%; and Social Media Monitoring Tools 8,7% (Figure 4). The tool with less percentage assigned were the Collaborative Workspaces (8%), which reaffirms the need to create a community in which these spaces are implemented. This collaborative workspace could be conceived in support to the most applied tools, such as web scraping and monitoring tools.

Figure 4. Bar chart illustrating the frequency with which different tools were utilized by participants in the survey. Respondents were asked to distribute 100 points across multiple items, reflecting the relative importance of each tool in their workflow (n =22).

Each user indicates the support of an average of four tools to conduct HS activities, among which, three are open to external users. These open access tools could be relevant in case of creation of collaborative spaces between different institutions.

Some of tools mentioned by the participants were:

Biodiversity and Taxonomy databases (GBIF; Plant pest-host lists; WFO (World Flora Online)); Open scientific databases (USDA fungal-host database; NCBI Biobank/Genbank; iNaturalist); Data Analysis and Visualization Tools (R software packages as Bibliometrix (for quantitative analysis and statistics to publications), *btm* (for topic modeling), *rgbif* (for species occurrence - mapping), *taxize* (for synonym and general taxonomic corrections), Gephi, Vosviewer,); Information Retrieval and Communication Tools (ProMED, CABI ISC, Google Scholar, Publish or Perish, Social Media, Web of Science; University web pages, EPPO Global Database and reporting service); Data Processing and Analysis Tools (Medisys and EIOS, web scraping and text mining)

The relevance of the application of AI techniques to HS activity was supported by 73% of users. The main purposes for AI would be to facilitate the work by summarising massive datasets (including text) combined with highly multivariate quantitative analyses, finding patterns and relationships (clustering), and extracting key information from text and images. The intention to use machine learning to facilitate and improve the processes currently in use was also raised. This tool is highly valuable for HS, where vast amounts of data have to be reviewed and prioritized for reporting and where the time factor is crucial to the relevant of the service.

When participants were asked about their intention to be involved in HS in the near future (approximately within the next two years). A positive trend was obtained (average of +27,8% increase in time; 58% of positive answers). Only one participant expressed a decrease in willingness to participate (-80%), while seven participants indicated no change in their commitment level.

Workshop participants highlighted the following key takeaways:

- **Need for standardization:** the field of HS lacks the discipline and established methodologies compared to other scientific fields. The need to find a standard terminology would be essential for effective communication and collaboration. Moreover, due to expert judgment, current methods tend to introduce a significant bias. Interaction network modelling may be considered.

- Artificial intelligence: as future potential, using AI approach hold promise for more accurate and impactful HS.

Collaboration and Openness: collaboration across disciplines and open sharing of data and processes are crucial for improvement. Multidisciplinary approaches should be considered to improve our outputs, such as considering underlying drivers and longer-term threats or quantitative analysis. Collaboration and community building is one of the main objectives of this workshop. Furthermore, this issue emerged as a priority and necessity throughout the discussions. However, in order to create a good basis, the participants were asked to identify possible obstacles to their involvement in such community. The main arguments were:

- Lack of coordination: Discussions around HS can be undisciplined (as previous spotted with the need for standardization) and there is a difficulty integrating research findings into practical application. The application of concerted methods and some centralized coordination would be pivotal to its success.
- Resource constraints: time limitations due to workload or other commitments, lack of dedicated funding, and limited access to required tools and technologies were all mentioned as potential barriers.

On the other hand, the motivations that would lead to participation in the community were also asked:

- improved HS activity, its outputs and efficiency;
- shared knowledge and learning and gain professional development;
- help to manage agricultural and environmental challenges.

Overall, the feedback given by participants was interpreted as positive and such as was high the interest expressed in continuing sharing information and in discussing further about tools and methodology (spatial information, text mining activities, hotspots, etc).

Conclusions and recommendations

A number of observations collected during the workshops were identified as take-home messages.

- HS experience can be overarching the specific expertise on biological invasion

The specific expertise of this workshop participants was quite different and frequently distant, in spite of the common topic of biological invasions. This was perceived as an asset, although social scientists were poorly represented. Also the final goal was common: to satisfy the specific needs of each final user/audience, which is not necessarily represented by risk managers for all participants. However, sharing the individual experiences and achievements favours improvements in the individual fields of activity.

However, risk managers should be considered not only final recipients of the HS outcomes but also involved as active actors in the process, in order to ensure the most efficient use of resources and fit for purpose products. Not only they should be part of the process to understand at the best the way it works and to indicate priorities but also to recognise its relevance and potential.

This conclusion is intrinsically reflected in the agenda of next and second workshop, fully dedicated to the final user (i.e.: risk managers) of HS activity: what means “successful” in HS activity?

- Moving from environmental scanning to horizon scanning

The way information is published in the web and scraping is conducted makes that many important events go undetected or detected too late (e.g. *Solenopsis invicta*: signals on media were available but the scientific publication indicating the outbreak in Sicily arrived much later). Efforts should be put in moving from a consequence→event to event→consequence tracing. AI should help accelerate the alert systems allocating human activity more towards expert evaluation of content. Another step in support to a farsighted approach is moving from a species-oriented to drivers-oriented scanning: this would extend the focus to processes and to the possibility of modelling them. The drivers-oriented approach would be also coherent the One Health framework, as its prerequisite is a transdisciplinary and multisectoral view that interconnects people, animals, plants, and their shared environment. In accordance with the introduction above, this change in the approach will be the subject of the third workshop dedicated to HS in plant health.

- How much an open (multidisciplinary) community could be beneficial

If the importance of moving from environmental to horizon scanning is recognised, then the composition of expert groups and the interconnection between process components must be rethought. This doesn't strictly mean only favouring global perspectives but being able to work in a modular manner defining the granularity of the analysis according to needs. For example, EIOS allows organising the activities in communities and boards that can focus on global, regional or local needs without losing connection among members and would also allow dialogue among communities with different targets. This would be again in line with One Health approach. However, a series of prerequisites for creating a community have been identified.

The definition of a cross-cutting vocabulary on HS, at least for the basic terms. For instance, even when the word *threat* may be understood in the same way by different experts, what is signalled as a *threat* may differ among them.

- the mapping of the community

- the analysis of the available tools and software for text mining, web scraping, spatial information, etc

The composition of a community would be pivotal to an evolution in the way HS is performed today, with a reorganisation in resources, sharing of knowledge and technologies in favour of a more rapid reaction and outputs easier to track, connect and share.

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
CABI	CAB International
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EIOS	Epidemic Intelligence from Open Sources
EPPO	European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization
HS	Horizon Scanning
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LLM	Large Language Models
NPPO	National Plant Protection Organism
WHO	World Health Organization

Appendix A – List of participants

List of the participants, affiliation and mode of participation during the event.

Participant	Institution - Country	Modality
Louise Barwell	Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (CEH) - England	Online
Bernard Bottex	EFSA Knowledge, Innovation and Partnership Management (KNOW) Unit - Italy	Online
Andy Bourke	Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM) - Ireland	In person
Giuseppe Brundu	University of Sassari - Italy	In person
Susan Canavan	University of Galway - Ireland	In person
Martina Cendoya Martinez	Valencian Institute for Agricultural Research (IVIA) - Spain	In person
Jennifer Cook	North Carolina State University - United States of America	Online
James Cullum	CABI - England	In person
Roger Day	CABI - England	Online
Brian Doherty	European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC) - Italy	In person
Ken Fening	University of Ghana	Online
Hannah Fielder	CABI - England	In person
Emmanuel Gachet	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES) - France	In person
Pablo Gonzalez	University of Cordoba - Spain	Online
Quentin Groom	Meise Botanic Garden - Belgium	In person
Philip Hulme	Lincoln University - New Zealand	In person
Josep Jaques	Universitat Jaume I - Spain	Online
Paul Kachapulula	University of Zambia	Online
Yahya Kandeh	Africa Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) - Southern Africa	Online
Kristina Kovacicova	European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC), DISINFO team of the Unit T5 (Text mining and data mining) - Italy	Online
Magali Larenaudie	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES) - France	In person
Marianne Loiseau	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES) - France	In person
Elizabete Marchante	Centre for Functional Ecology, University of Coimbra - Portugal	In person
Lucie Michel	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE) - France	In person
Cindy Morris	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE) - France	In person
Claire Nédellec	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE) - France	In person
Berit Nordskog	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO)	Online
MaryLucy Oronje	CABI - Kenya	Online
Shyam Phartyal	Nalanda University - India	Online

Philippe Reignault	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES) - France	In person
María Ribaya	EFSA Environment, Plants and Ecotoxicology Unit (PLANTS) - Italy	In person
Godshen Robert	North Carolina State University - United States of America	Online
Mathieu Roche	French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development (CIRAD)	In person
Ivan Rwomushana	CABI - Kenya	Online
Johannes Schnitzler	World Health Organization (WHO) - Germany	Online
Wojciech Solarz	Institute of Nature Conservation, Polish Academy of Sciences	In person
Joseph Stinziano	Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA)	Online
Muriel Suffert	European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization (EPPO) - France	In person
Paolo Tizzani	World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) - France	In person
Sara Tramontini	EFSA Environment, Plants and Ecotoxicology Unit (PLANTS) - Italy	In person
Piotr Tryjanowski	Poznan University of Life Sciences - Poland	In person
Ahmet Uludağ	Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University (ÇOMU) - Türkiye	In person
Jaap van Kretschmar	North Carolina State University - United States of America	Online
Montserrat Vilà	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) and University of Sevilla - Spain	Online
Sybren Vos	EFSA Environment, Plants and Ecotoxicology Unit (PLANTS) - Italy	In person

Appendix B – Agenda of the event

Tuesday 9 th April		
Sharing experiences on Horizon Scanning		
14:00-14:15 CEST	Welcoming speech	Philippe Reignault - Head of ANSES Plant Health Laboratory & Scientific Director for Plant Health
14:15-14:45	Brainstorm about Horizon Scanning	Maria Ribaya – Trainee - EFSA Environment, plants and ecotoxicology unit Brian Doherty - Project Manager – Text Mining and Analysis Unit, European Commission Joint Research Centre
14:45-15:30	Keynote Horizon Scanning: The Future Starts Today (20' + Q/A)	Philip Hulme - Distinguished Professor of Plant Biosecurity, Centre for One Biosecurity Research, Analysis and Synthesis, Lincoln University, NZ
15:30-16:30	World café	
16:30-17:00	Horizon Scanning activity on Plant Health in EFSA (20' + Q/A)	Sara Tramontini Project coordinator – EFSA Environment, plants and ecotoxicology unit Magali Larenaudie – Scientific officer - Plant Health Laboratory, ANSES
17:00-17:30	Keynote Sustainable plant production based on insight from One Health: what will be the scope and targets for horizon scanning? (20' + Q/A)	Cindy E. Morris – Research director – Plant pathology unit, INRAe
18:30-19:00	Wrap up	Brian Doherty - Project Manager – Text Mining and Analysis Unit, European Commission Joint Research Centre
19:30	Pickup time in front of the hotel by shuttle	
20:00–23:30	Dinner	

Wednesday 10 th April		
Horizon scanning : Tools and Methodologies		
9:00-9:35 CEST	Keynote On the Horizon: Identifying invasive species threats in the United States (20' + Q/A)	Susan Canavan – Botanist, Horizon Scanning Consultant
9:35	Group picture	
9:45-10:15	World cafe	
10:15-10:45	Experiences and tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mathieu Roche: Text mining • James Cullum: AI tool for reducing noise
10:45-10:50	Coffee break	
10:50-11:30	Presentation of EIOS (15'+Q/A)	Johannes Schnitzler – Technology coordinator - EIOS Core team WHO
11:30-11:50	Analysis of disinformation narratives: climate change (15'+Q/A)	Kristina Kovacicova – Machine learning specialist – European Commission Joint Research Centre, DISINFO unit
11:50-13:00	Wrap up / conclusions Q/A	Brian Doherty - Project Manager – Text Mining and Analysis Unit, European Commission Joint Research Centre
13:00	Closing of the event	